

showed that some were seriously damaged. The percentage of infested leaves varied from 28.2 on the variety

Jyothi to 51.5 on Thriveni. That suggests that the thrip shows some varietal preference or nonpreference. The grass

Panicum repens, which grows abundantly on field bunds, is an alternate host for the insect. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Dry matter and nitrogen accumulation in two semidwarf indica rices in rainfed-upland conditions

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The accumulation of dry matter and nitrogen in two semidwarf indica rices, Padma and Bala, under rainfed-upland culture was studied in a field trial during the kharif (wet) season of 1972 and 1973 at the Crop Research Center of the G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar. Seeds were drilled in a dry seedbed at 60 kg/ha in rows 23 cm apart. Four nitrogen levels (30, 60, 90, and 120 kg/ha) and 5 application methods were used.

Padma and Bala did not differ markedly in the accumulation of dry matter up to the heading stage (see fig. a). But interestingly, the rate of dry matter accumulation from heading to maturity was higher in Bala than in Padma. That indicates that Bala had better photosynthetic ability than Padma during the postheading period, which was probably the main reason for its higher dry matter accumulation and, consequently, higher grain yield at maturity (see table). Bala had higher concentrations of nitrogen than Padma at all growth stages except tillering in 1972 (fig. b). But in 1973 nitrogen concentration was higher in Bala only until heading; afterwards, that in Padma was higher. In both years, the nitrogen concentration in the plants of the two varieties decreased linearly from panicle initiation to 15 days after heading (DH), but in 1972 that in Padma decreased

Dry-matter yield (a), nitrogen concentration (b) and nitrogen uptake (c) at various stages of growth of two dwarf indica rices. T = tillering (40 DS), PI = panicle initiation (60 DS), H = heading (86 DS), 15 DH (days after heading, 101 DS), M = maturity (111 DS), DS = days after sowing.

linearly from tillering to 15 DH.

Bala plants absorbed more nitrogen from the soil than Padma plants at all growth stages in both years (fig. c). The difference was greater during the postheading period. The nitrogen uptake in Bala grains at maturity was higher than that in Padma, but that in Padma's straw

was higher (see table). Padma and Bala removed an average of 58 and 63 kg N/ha, respectively, at maturity. Bala translocated to its grains about 74% of the absorbed nitrogen; Padma translocated 69%. The data show that Bala performs better than Padma in rainfed-upland culture. □

Dry matter yield, nitrogen concentration, and nitrogen uptake at maturity in two semidwarf indica rices under rainfed-upland conditions. Pantnagar, India.

Particulars	Padma		Bala		S. Em.±		CD 5% ^b	
	1972	1973	1972	1973	1972	1973	1972	1973
Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	2.91	4.07	3.22	4.50	0.106	0.068	ns	0.205
Straw yield ^a (t/ha)	2.44	3.36	2.68	3.39	0.072	0.067	0.219	ns
N in grain (%)	1.10	1.18	1.20	1.22	0.011	0.009	0.034	0.029
N in straw (%)	0.66	0.64	0.55	0.52	0.007	0.009	0.020	0.028
N uptake of grain (kg/ha)	32.08	47.99	39.01	55.12	1.46	0.91	4.42	2.75
N uptake of straw (kg/ha)	15.19	21.42	14.88	17.68	0.44	0.63	ns	1.91
Total N uptake (kg/ha)	41.27	69.41	53.89	72.80	1.75	1.75	5.31	ns

^aA sum of grain and straw yields would represent total dry matter at maturity.

^bns = not significant.